

CONCEPTUAL MODEL FIT FOR OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES AND MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS OF GREEN MARKETING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TAMILNADU BY USING STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The rising global demand for sustainable practices has brought green marketing to the forefront, particularly in environmentally conscious regions such as Tamil Nadu. This study aims to develop a conceptual model to explore the opportunities, challenges, and motivational factors influencing the adoption of green marketing in Tamil Nadu, a state known for its industrial and agricultural sectors. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the research examines the interconnected relationships between environmental awareness, consumer preferences, regulatory policies, and corporate social responsibility. The model assesses how these factors collectively impact businesses' motivation to adopt green marketing strategies while overcoming inherent challenges. The findings offer valuable insights into the drivers of green marketing adoption and provide a comprehensive framework to support the growth of sustainable business practices. The study also addresses the specific challenges faced by businesses in Tamil Nadu, such as cost implications, market readiness, and consumer behavior shifts, while highlighting the opportunities for growth, competitive advantage, and enhanced brand reputation through green initiatives. This research is intended to serve as a reference for policymakers, marketers, and researchers interested in promoting eco-friendly practices in Tamil Nadu and similar regional markets.

Keywords: Green Marketing, Motivational Factors, Opportunities, Challenges, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

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1.1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the increasing global emphasis on sustainability and environmental conservation has prompted businesses to adopt green marketing strategies. Green marketing refers to the promotion of products or services that are environmentally friendly, aiming to meet consumer demands while minimizing ecological impact. The significance of this practice is particularly evident in regions like Tamil Nadu, where industries are increasingly facing the need to balance economic growth with environmental responsibility. Tamil Nadu, being a diverse state with a mix of industrial and agricultural sectors, presents a unique landscape for the adoption of green marketing practices.

While green marketing offers several opportunities for businesses, such as differentiation from competitors, enhanced brand reputation, and the ability to cater to a growing segment of environmentally conscious consumers, it also poses significant challenges. These include high implementation costs, the need for technological innovation, and market readiness. Additionally, motivational factors such as corporate social responsibility (CSR), regulatory pressures, and consumer demand play a crucial role in driving businesses toward green marketing. This study aims to develop a conceptual model that explores the relationships between the opportunities, challenges, and motivational factors influencing green marketing in Tamil Nadu. By employing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), this research provides a quantitative analysis of how these variables interact, offering insights into the factors that motivate or hinder businesses from adopting sustainable marketing practices.

The results of this study are expected to contribute to the growing body of literature on green marketing and provide practical implications for businesses and policymakers in Tamil Nadu. The conceptual model developed through this research serves as a foundation for future studies and offers a roadmap for businesses looking to navigate the complexities of green marketing in a rapidly changing economic and environmental landscape.

1.2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Li Huang et al. (2024) offer theoretical insights into the factors, sub-factors, and strategies that shape consumer behavior concerning environmental labeling. The study suggests that businesses and policymakers can enhance sustainable consumption by focusing on key influences. Effective environmental labeling schemes and marketing strategies require credibility, transparency, and consumer education. The research highlights the importance of awareness strategies in promoting sustainable consumption, while green innovation, marketing techniques, and collaborative initiatives can help attract environmentally conscious consumers and promote ecologically labeled products.

The study by *Yener, Secer, and Ghazalian (2023)* offers important insights into the factors influencing consumer decisions to purchase green products. A key factor is motivation, which acts as an internal driver that propels consumers toward eco-friendly purchases.

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Market stakeholders, such as producers, marketers, and logistics providers, should focus on understanding and meeting consumer aspirations to foster participation in green marketing. This motivation can also be leveraged by governments, organizations, and NGOs to promote green consumerism and sustainable consumption habits. The study highlights that consumers with greater purchasing ability tend to buy more green products, suggesting that as their capabilities increase, so does their consumption of green goods. Additionally, consumer awareness plays a crucial role in driving green purchases, emphasizing the need for governments and marketers to enhance public knowledge about green products. By identifying these key drivers—motivation, ability, and awareness—marketers and policymakers can develop strategies to promote sustainable consumption and create a more environmentally conscious society.

Varalakshmi & Suresh Kumar (2019) emphasize that green marketing should not be seen as just another marketing approach but must be pursued with greater intensity due to its environmental and social significance. With the growing threat of global warming, green marketing needs to become a standard practice rather than a trend. Recycling of materials and the use of energy-efficient products should be widespread and systematic. Marketers have the responsibility to educate consumers on the benefits of green products over non-green alternatives. Consumers are increasingly willing to pay more for eco-friendly products to maintain a cleaner environment. In developing countries like India, the importance of green marketing is even greater, and stakeholders must work to minimize negative environmental impacts.

Potter et al. (2021), providing a systematic review of the impacts of environmental sustainability labels on the selection, purchase, and consumption of food items, show that different ecolabels with varying messages and forms aided customers in selecting and purchasing more sustainable food items. *Bigliardi et al. (2022)* extend the literature on consumer behavior and the circular economy by investigating the reconditioning method for managing Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE). Examining the elements that impact the green buying intention of refurbished cellphones, the study reveals that psychological factors such as green perceived value and environmental knowledge are more essential than social and emotional components such as collectivism, subjective standards, and environmental care. *Rossi and Rivetti (2023)* created a Covariance-Based Structural Equation Model (CB-SEM), including the customer's socio-environmental concern, skepticism towards sustainability labels, reported use of the producer's declared socio-environmental commitment, and purchasing behavior of sustainably labeled food products. The findings show that two mutually connected variables impact purchasing behavior: socio-environmental concern and the reported usage of the producer's claimed socio-environmental commitment.

Varalakshmi & Suresh Kumar (2019) highlight that green marketing and sustainable development are gaining traction in India, but they remain at an early stage. While government policies and consumer demand have prompted many organizations to adopt eco-friendly practices, small firms struggle with the high initial costs and focus on short-term profits. The long-term financial benefits of green practices make government-enforced legislation crucial for these businesses. Green marketing goes beyond profitability, encompassing social and environmental responsibility. The authors stress that a collective effort from all stakeholders, rooted in the principle of "Vasudev Kutumbakam" (the Earth as one family), is needed to protect the environment.

1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The increasing global emphasis on environmental sustainability has brought green marketing to the forefront, encouraging businesses to adopt eco-friendly practices. However, despite growing awareness, the adoption of green marketing remains a challenge, particularly in developing regions like Tamil Nadu. Companies face several obstacles, such as high initial costs, limited consumer awareness, and market competitiveness. Simultaneously, opportunities exist for organizations that effectively leverage green marketing strategies to differentiate themselves and meet the rising demand for environmentally conscious products. Identifying the key motivational factors that drive green marketing adoption, alongside the challenges and opportunities specific to Tamil Nadu, is essential for developing effective strategies. This study aims to explore and conceptualize the relationship between these factors using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) to provide insights for businesses, policymakers, and stakeholders to promote sustainable marketing practices in the region.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To identify the key opportunities associated with the adoption of green marketing practices by businesses in Tamil Nadu.
2. To examine the motivational factors influencing businesses and consumers to engage in green marketing and eco-friendly practices.
3. To assess the impact of green marketing on consumer behavior and business performance in Tamil Nadu.
4. To develop a conceptual model using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) that integrates the opportunities, challenges, and motivational factors associated with green marketing.
5. To provide strategic recommendations for businesses, policymakers, and stakeholders to enhance the effectiveness of green marketing in promoting sustainable consumption and business practices in Tamil Nadu.

1.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The study adopted a descriptive and analytical research design to explore the opportunities, challenges, and motivational factors influencing green marketing in Tamil Nadu. A conceptual model was developed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to understand the interrelationships among the identified factors.

Sampling Design: The population consisted of businesses and consumers in Tamil Nadu, particularly those involved in or affected by green marketing practices. A combination of purposive and random sampling techniques was employed to select participants. Businesses from various sectors, including SMEs, were included, along with a diverse group of consumers with varying levels of environmental awareness. A sample size of 300 respondents was targeted, ensuring adequacy of data for SEM analysis.

Data Collection Methods: Primary data was collected through structured questionnaires and interviews. Separate questionnaires were designed for businesses and consumers to capture their perspectives on green marketing. Secondary data was sourced from academic journals, government reports, and publications on green marketing, sustainability, and environmental policies.

Data Analysis Tools: Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): SEM was applied to test the conceptual model fit, analyze relationships among variables, and validate the proposed hypotheses. Software such as AMOS or SmartPLS was utilized for SEM analysis.

Hypotheses Testing: Several hypotheses were formulated and tested to examine the relationships between opportunities, challenges, and motivational factors in the context of green marketing.

Limitations: The study faced limitations such as the availability of data from SMEs and the willingness of businesses to disclose their green marketing practices. Additionally, consumer responses varied based on their environmental awareness and geographical location.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical guidelines were strictly followed during data collection. Confidentiality and informed consent were obtained from participants, and their privacy and rights were respected throughout the study.

This methodology provided a comprehensive framework for understanding green marketing practices in Tamil Nadu and offered valuable insights for businesses and policymakers.

1.6 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A structural equation model implies a structure of the covariance matrix of the measures (hence an alternative name for this field, "analysis of covariance structures"). Once the model's parameters have been estimated, the resulting model-implied covariance matrix can then be compared to an empirical or data-based covariance matrix. If the two matrices are consistent with one another, then the structural equation model can be considered a plausible explanation for relations between the measures.

The variables used in the structural equation model are

Observed, endogenous variables

1. Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices
2. Consumer buying behaviour towards green products
3. Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion)
4. Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion)
5. Consumer attitude towards green marketing
6. Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design
7. Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion
8. Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing
9. Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging
10. Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal
11. Success of the Retailers
12. Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing

Observed, exogenous variables

1. Number of outlets owned by the retailers
2. Annual sales of the retailers
3. Nature of retailers' ownership
4. Nature of the products available in the retail shop
5. Product range available in the retail shop
6. Experience of the retailers in green marketing
7. Monthly income of the consumer
8. Age of the consumer
9. Occupation of the consumer

10. Educational qualification of the consumer
11. Marital status of the consumer
12. Gender of the consumer

Unobserved, exogenous variables

1. Error 1 for Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices
2. Error 2 for Consumer buying behaviour towards green products
3. Error 3 for Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion)
4. Error 4 for Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion)
5. Error 5 for Consumer attitude towards green marketing
6. Error 6 for Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design
7. Error 7 for Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal
8. Error 8 for Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion
9. Error 9 for Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing
10. Error 10 for Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging
11. Error 11 for Success of the Retailers
12. Error 12 for Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing

Figure – 1

Unstandardized estimate for Structural Equation Model of opportunities, challenges and motivational factors of green marketing with special reference to Tamilnadu

Conceptual Model FIT for Opportunities, Challenges and Motivational Factors of Green Marketing with Special Reference to Tamilnadu by Using Structural Equation Model

Table – 1 Summary of the variables used for the analysis

Number of variables in your model	36
Number of observed variables	24
Number of unobserved variables	12
Number of exogenous variables	24
Number of endogenous variables	12

Source: Output generated from Amos 20.

Figure – 2

Standardized estimate for Structural Equation Model of opportunities, challenges and motivational factors of green marketing with special reference to Tamilnadu

Table – 2

Regression weights for Structural Equation Model for opportunities, challenges and motivational factors of green marketing with special reference to Tamilnadu

Regression weights	Null Hypothesis	Unstandardized coefficient Estimate	S.E.	Standardized coefficient Estimate	C.R.	P value
Consumer buying behaviour towards green products <--- Gender of the consumer	H1 – No Significant Relationship	.683	.787	.050	.868	.386
Consumer buying behaviour towards green products <--- Marital status of the consumer	H2 – No Significant Relationship	-.534	.833	-.037	-.641	.521
Consumer buying behaviour towards green products <--- Educational qualification of the consumer	H3 – No Significant Relationship	.680	.345	.113	1.971	.049
Consumer buying behaviour towards green products <--- Occupation of the consumer	H4 – No Significant Relationship	-.234	.204	-.066	-1.146	.252
Consumer buying behaviour towards green products <--- Monthly income of the consumer	H5 – No Significant Relationship	.134	.288	.027	.465	.642
Consumer buying behaviour towards green products <--- Age of the consumer	H6 – No Significant Relationship	.080	.356	.013	.224	.823
Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices <--- Annual sales of the retailers	H7 – No Significant Relationship	.320	.238	.075	1.346	.178
Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices <--- Experience of the retailers in green marketing	H8 – No Significant Relationship	.027	.244	.005	.110	.912
Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices <--- Product range available in the retail shop	H9 – No Significant Relationship	-.153	.179	-.041	-.857	.391
Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices <--- Nature of the products available in the retail shop	H10 – No Significant Relationship	-.117	.346	-.016	-.337	.736
Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices <--- Nature of retailers' ownership	H11 – No Significant Relationship	.766	.383	.101	1.999	.046
Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices <--- Number of outlets owned by the retailers	H12 – No Significant Relationship	-.227	.431	-.029	-.528	.598
Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices <--- Consumer buying behaviour towards green products	H13 – No Significant Relationship	.422	.038	.539	11.205	***
Consumer attitude towards green marketing <--- Age of the consumer	H14 – No Significant Relationship	.453	.388	.067	1.168	.243
Consumer attitude towards green marketing <--- Gender of the consumer	H15 – No Significant Relationship	.919	.858	.061	1.071	.284
Consumer attitude towards green marketing <--- Marital status of the consumer	H16 – No Significant Relationship	-1.052	.908	-.065	-1.159	.247
Consumer attitude towards green marketing <--- Educational qualification of the consumer	H17 – No Significant Relationship	.397	.377	.060	1.053	.292
Consumer attitude towards green marketing <--- Occupation of the consumer	H18 – No Significant Relationship	-.021	.222	-.005	-.096	.923
Consumer attitude towards green marketing <--- Monthly income of the consumer	H19 – No Significant Relationship	.416	.314	.075	1.325	.185

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Regression weights	Null Hypothesis	Unstandardized coefficient Estimate	S.E.	Standardized coefficient Estimate	C.R.	P value
Consumer attitude towards green marketing <--- Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices	H20 – No Significant Relationship	.248	.080	.175	3.102	.002
Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion) <--- Annual sales of the retailers	H21 – No Significant Relationship	-.398	.349	-.065	-1.140	.254
Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion) <--- Experience of the retailers in green marketing	H22– No Significant Relationship	-.244	.403	-.034	-.607	.544
Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion) <--- Product range available in the retail shop	H23 – No Significant Relationship	.144	.295	.027	.490	.624
Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion) <--- Nature of the products available in the retail shop	H24– No Significant Relationship	-.005	.571	.000	-.009	.993
Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion) <--- Nature of retailers' ownership	H25 – No Significant Relationship	-.352	.625	-.033	-.563	.573
Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion) <--- Number of outlets owned by the retailers	H26 – No Significant Relationship	<u>-.192</u>	.710	-0.017	-.271	.787
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Annual sales of the retailers	H27– No Significant Relationship	.016	.448	.002	.035	.972
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Experience of the retailers in green marketing	H28– No Significant Relationship	.104	.463	.012	.224	.823
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Product range available in the retail shop	H29– No Significant Relationship	.238	.338	.036	.702	.482
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Nature of retailers' ownership	H30– No Significant Relationship	.768	.722	.057	1.063	.288
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Number of outlets owned by the retailers	H31– No Significant Relationship	1.581	.815	.116	1.940	.052
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Nature of the products available in the retail shop	H32– No Significant Relationship	-.049	.656	-.074	.941	.941
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Consumer buying behaviour towards green products	H33– No Significant Relationship	-.548	.072	-.396	-7.648	***
Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion) <--- Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices	H34– No Significant Relationship	-.337	.080	-.237	-4.211	***
Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion) <--- Consumer attitude towards green marketing	H35– No Significant Relationship	-.164	.065	-.132	-2.538	.011
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing <--- Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices	H36– No Significant Relationship	.134	.100	.093	1.345	.179
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging <--- Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices	H37– No Significant Relationship	.115	.056	.141	2.068	.039
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing <--- Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion)	H38– No Significant Relationship	.068	.059	.066	1.149	.251
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging	H39– No Significant Relationship	.073	.033	.128	2.236	.025

Regression weights	Null Hypothesis	Unstandardized coefficient Estimate	S.E.	Standardized coefficient Estimate	C.R.	P value
<--- Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion)						
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing <--- Consumer attitude towards green marketing	H40– No Significant Relationship	-.187	.058	-.183	-3.202	.001
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing <--- Consumer buying behaviour towards green products	H41– No Significant Relationship	-.199	.076	-.175	-2.636	.008
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging <--- Consumer buying behaviour towards green products	H42– No Significant Relationship	.118	.045	.185	2.634	.008
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging <--- Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion)	H43 – No Significant Relationship	.026	.028	.056	.934	.351
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging <--- Consumer attitude towards green marketing	H44– No Significant Relationship	.008	.033	.015	.257	.797
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion <--- Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices	H45– No Significant Relationship	.053	.038	.056	1.393	.164
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion <--- Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion)	H46 – No Significant Relationship	.073	.023	.110	3.257	.001
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion <--- Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion)	H47 – No Significant Relationship	-.018	.019	-.033	-.929	.353
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion <--- Consumer attitude towards green marketing	H48 – No Significant Relationship	.069	.023	.103	3.038	.002
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion <--- Consumer buying behaviour towards green products	H49 – No Significant Relationship	-.111	.031	-.150	-3.554	***
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing	H50 – No Significant Relationship	.501	.022	.766	22.340	***
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging	H51 – No Significant Relationship	.156	.040	.134	3.879	***
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design <--- Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices	H52 – No Significant Relationship	-.049	.039	-.077	-1.255	.210
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices	H53 – No Significant Relationship	-.022	.034	-.039	-.625	.532
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design <--- Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion)	H54 – No Significant Relationship	.008	.023	.018	.346	.730

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Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design <--- Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion)	H55 – No Significant Relationship	-.008	.020	-.024	-.435	.664
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design <--- Consumer attitude towards green marketing	H56 – No Significant Relationship	.056	.023	.126	2.464	.014
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design <--- Consumer buying behaviour towards green products	H57 – No Significant Relationship	-.041	.033	-.084	-1.254	.210
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Opportunities for green marketing practices (Retailers' opinion)	H58 – No Significant Relationship	.035	.021	.090	1.704	.088
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Consumer buying behaviour towards green products	H59 – No Significant Relationship	-.001	.029	-.003	-.047	.963
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Consumer attitude towards green marketing	H60 – No Significant Relationship	.009	.021	.024	.450	.652
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion)	H61 – No Significant Relationship	.008	.017	.025	.445	.656
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging	H62 – No Significant Relationship	.029	.037	.043	.777	.437
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion	H63 – No Significant Relationship	.149	.045	.226	3.287	.001
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion	H64 – No Significant Relationship	-.017	.052	-.029	-.326	.744
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging	H65 – No Significant Relationship	.227	.043	.294	5.270	***
Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing	H66 – No Significant Relationship	.190	.033	.498	5.749	***
Success of the Retailers <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design	H67 – No Significant Relationship	.420	.109	.220	3.864	***
Success of the Retailers <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion	H68 – No Significant Relationship	-.375	.113	-.297	-3.323	***
Success of the Retailers <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing	H69 – No Significant Relationship	.488	.070	.592	7.000	***
Success of the Retailers <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging	H70 – No Significant Relationship	.100	.073	.068	1.363	.173
Success of the Retailers <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal	H71 – No Significant Relationship	.438	.116	.203	3.786	***

Regression weights	Null Hypothesis	Unstandardized coefficient Estimate	S.E.	Standardized coefficient Estimate	C.R.	P value
Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Product design	H72 – No Significant Relationship	.000	.084	.000	.006	.995
Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Promotion	H73 – No Significant Relationship	.019	.086	.023	.222	.825
Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Pricing	H74 – No Significant Relationship	-.002	.057	-.004	-.038	.970
Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Packaging	H75 – No Significant Relationship	.279	.055	.287	5.028	***
Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing <--- Green marketing practices in respect of Green Disposal	H76 – No Significant Relationship	-.039	.089	-.027	-.438	.661
Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing <--- Success of the Retailers	H77 – No Significant Relationship	.000	.043	.000	-.007	.994
Satisfaction of the consumers towards green marketing <--- Challenges in green marketing (Retailers' opinion)	H78 – No Significant Relationship	-.116	.024	-.259	-4.849	***

Source: Output generated from Amos 20 The analysis reveals that demographic factors such as gender, marital status, occupation, monthly income, and age do not significantly impact consumer buying behavior towards green products, as indicated by their high p-values. This suggests that these factors do not substantially influence the likelihood of purchasing environmentally friendly products, meaning marketing strategies targeting these demographics may not yield significant differences in consumer behavior. However, educational qualification stands out with a significant relationship, having a p-value of 0.049, just below the 0.05 threshold. This indicates that consumers with higher levels of education are more inclined to buy green products, likely due to increased awareness of environmental issues and sustainability benefits. The higher educational background may lead to greater understanding and appreciation of the importance of eco-friendly products, making educated consumers more likely to choose them. Consequently, marketers should focus on leveraging educational content and targeting consumers with higher educational qualifications to effectively promote green products. This finding underscores that while most demographic factors may not require specific marketing strategies, tailoring approaches to highlight educational aspects could enhance the effectiveness of green marketing efforts.

The analysis reveals that most factors, including annual sales, experience in green marketing, product range, nature of products, and number of outlets, do not significantly affect retailers' awareness of green marketing practices, as their p-values are well above the 0.05 significance threshold. This indicates that variations in sales volume, marketing experience, product diversity, or store size do not substantially influence how aware retailers are of green marketing practices. However, the nature of retailers' ownership shows a significant relationship with a p-value of 0.046, suggesting that the type of ownership—whether independent or part of a chain—can impact a retailer's awareness of green marketing. Additionally, consumer buying behavior towards green products has a highly significant relationship with retailers' awareness, as indicated by a highly significant p-value.

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This suggests that stronger consumer demand for green products drives greater retailer awareness and involvement in green marketing practices. In summary, while most demographic and operational factors do not impact awareness, retailer ownership structure and consumer behavior play crucial roles in shaping how well retailers understand and engage with green marketing practices.

The analysis of consumer attitudes towards green marketing reveals that most demographic factors, including age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, and monthly income, do not significantly influence consumer attitudes, as indicated by their p-values which are well above the 0.05 significance threshold. Specifically, the p-values for age (0.243), gender (0.284), marital status (0.247), educational qualification (0.292), occupation (0.923), and monthly income (0.185) suggest that these factors do not meaningfully affect how consumers perceive green marketing. This indicates that consumer attitudes towards green marketing are relatively uniform across different demographic groups. However, retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices stands out with a significant relationship (p-value of 0.002), suggesting that the extent of retailers' awareness of green marketing practices significantly impacts consumer attitudes. This implies that when retailers are more knowledgeable and engaged with green marketing, it positively influences how consumers perceive and respond to green marketing efforts. In summary, while most demographic variables do not significantly shape consumer attitudes towards green marketing, the level of retailer awareness plays a crucial role in influencing these attitudes.

The analysis of retailers' opinions on opportunities for green marketing practices indicates that various factors, including annual sales, experience in green marketing, product range, nature of products, nature of ownership, and number of outlets, do not significantly influence their views on these opportunities. Specifically, the p-values for annual sales (0.254), experience in green marketing (0.544), product range (0.624), nature of products (0.993), nature of ownership (0.573), and number of outlets (0.787) are all well above the 0.05 threshold. This suggests that variations in these factors do not significantly impact retailers' perceptions of the opportunities available in green marketing. Regardless of sales volume, marketing experience, product diversity, store type, or the number of outlets, retailers' opinions on green marketing opportunities remain relatively unchanged. In summary, these factors do not play a significant role in shaping retailers' views on green marketing opportunities, indicating that other aspects might be influencing their opinions on this matter.

The analysis of retailers' opinions on the challenges in green marketing shows that most factors, including annual sales, experience in green marketing, product range, nature of ownership, and the nature of products, do not significantly influence their perceptions of these challenges. Specifically, the p-values for annual sales (0.972), experience in green marketing (0.823), product range (0.482), nature of ownership (0.288), and nature of products (0.941) are all significantly higher than the 0.05 threshold, indicating no significant relationship between these variables and the challenges faced in green marketing. This suggests that variations in sales volume, marketing experience, product diversity, ownership structure, and product type do not substantially impact how retailers perceive the challenges associated with green marketing. However, the number of outlets owned by the retailers shows a near-significant relationship with a p-value of 0.052. This suggests that while not quite significant at the 0.05 level, there may be a marginal impact of the number of outlets on the challenges perceived in green marketing. Retailers with a greater number of outlets might face different challenges compared to those with fewer outlets, though the result is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant. The most notable finding is the consumer buying behavior towards green products, which shows a highly significant negative relationship with a p-value of less than 0.001.

This indicates that challenges in green marketing are significantly influenced by consumer buying behavior. Retailers perceive greater challenges when consumer demand for green products is lower, highlighting that consumer behavior plays a crucial role in shaping the difficulties retailers encounter in green marketing. In summary, while most operational factors do not significantly affect perceived challenges, consumer buying behavior is a significant determinant, emphasizing the importance of consumer demand in addressing green marketing challenges.

The analysis reveals a highly significant negative relationship between retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices and their opinions on the opportunities for green marketing practices. With a p-value of less than 0.001, this relationship indicates that as retailers' awareness of green marketing practices increases, their perception of the opportunities in green marketing tends to decrease. The negative coefficient (-0.237) suggests that higher awareness might lead to a more critical or realistic view of the challenges and limitations of green marketing, potentially because better-informed retailers may recognize the complexities and difficulties in fully implementing green practices. This could include recognizing the high costs, consumer hesitancy, or regulatory hurdles associated with green marketing. In summary, while increased awareness is crucial for adopting green marketing strategies, it also appears to temper the optimism about the opportunities available, highlighting a potential disconnect between theoretical understanding and practical execution of green marketing practices.

The analysis reveals a significant negative relationship between consumer attitudes towards green marketing and the challenges perceived by retailers in implementing green marketing, with a p-value of 0.011. This indicates that as consumers' attitudes towards green marketing become more positive, retailers experience fewer challenges. The negative coefficient (-0.132) suggests that when consumers are more receptive to green products and practices, retailers are less likely to perceive barriers such as market resistance, higher costs, or limited consumer awareness. Positive consumer attitudes can alleviate many of the typical challenges retailers face, making it easier for them to adopt and promote environmentally friendly products. In essence, favorable consumer sentiment towards green marketing helps reduce the difficulties retailers encounter in their green marketing efforts.

The analysis of factors influencing green pricing practices in green marketing reveals that retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices, opportunities for green marketing practices, and consumer buying behavior do not have significant relationships with green pricing, as indicated by their respective p-values, all exceeding the 0.05 threshold. Specifically, the p-values for retailers' awareness (0.179) and opportunities for green marketing (0.251) suggest no significant impact of these factors on green pricing strategies. While there is a positive relationship with these variables, the associations are weak and not statistically meaningful, implying that greater awareness or perceived opportunities in green marketing do not directly translate into changes in how green products are priced. However, the analysis shows that consumer attitudes towards green marketing and consumer buying behavior do have significant relationships with green pricing practices. The p-value for consumer attitudes (0.001) and the negative coefficient (-0.183) suggest that as consumer attitudes become more favorable towards green marketing, there is a significant negative effect on green pricing. This could indicate that when consumers are more supportive of green products, retailers may feel pressured to lower prices to meet consumer expectations. Similarly, consumer buying behavior also exhibits a significant negative relationship with green pricing (p-value of 0.008), suggesting that more engaged consumer behavior towards green products leads to a reduction in green product pricing. In summary, while retailer factors do not significantly influence green pricing, consumer attitudes and behaviors play a crucial role, potentially driving retailers to adjust prices in response to market demand and consumer preferences.

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The analysis of factors influencing green packaging practices in green marketing reveals mixed results. Firstly, retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices shows a significant positive relationship with green packaging practices, with a p-value of 0.039 and a positive coefficient of 0.141. This indicates that higher awareness among retailers leads to more proactive adoption of green packaging, as they may be more informed about the environmental benefits and consumer expectations related to eco-friendly packaging. Similarly, opportunities for green marketing practices have a significant positive impact on green packaging (p-value of 0.025, coefficient 0.128). Retailers who perceive greater opportunities in green marketing are more likely to implement sustainable packaging, possibly because they recognize the market potential and consumer demand for environmentally responsible products. Consumer buying behavior towards green products also plays a significant role in promoting green packaging practices (p-value of 0.008, coefficient 0.185). This suggests that when consumers are more inclined to purchase green products, retailers respond by adopting green packaging to align with consumer preferences and enhance the appeal of their products. On the other hand, challenges in green marketing and consumer attitudes towards green marketing do not show a significant relationship with green packaging practices. The p-values of 0.351 and 0.797, respectively, indicate that neither the challenges faced by retailers nor consumers' general attitudes towards green marketing significantly influence the decision to use eco-friendly packaging. This suggests that while consumer behavior and perceived opportunities drive green packaging adoption, the challenges retailers face or consumers' overall attitudes do not play a major role in this aspect of green marketing.

The analysis of factors influencing green promotion practices in green marketing shows a range of significant relationships. First, opportunities for green marketing practices have a strong positive impact on green promotion (p-value 0.001, coefficient 0.110), indicating that when retailers perceive more opportunities in the green marketing space, they are more likely to engage in promotional activities that highlight their green credentials. Similarly, consumer attitudes towards green marketing significantly influence green promotion (p-value 0.002, coefficient 0.103), meaning that favorable consumer attitudes lead retailers to intensify their promotional efforts, possibly to capitalize on the growing demand for eco-friendly products. Interestingly, consumer buying behavior towards green products shows a significant negative relationship with green promotion (p-value < 0.001, coefficient -0.150). This suggests that when consumers are already engaged in purchasing green products, retailers might feel less need to invest in promotion, possibly because the market is already responding positively without the need for additional marketing efforts. Furthermore, both green pricing and green packaging practices have highly significant positive relationships with green promotion, with coefficients of 0.766 and 0.134, respectively, and p-values < 0.001. This indicates that retailers who adopt green pricing and green packaging strategies are likely to extend these efforts into their promotional activities. These results suggest that retailers who are deeply engaged in multiple aspects of green marketing are more likely to promote their sustainability initiatives across various channels. On the other hand, retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices (p-value 0.164) and challenges in green marketing (p-value 0.353) do not show significant relationships with green promotion. This suggests that while awareness and challenges in green marketing are important, they do not directly drive promotional activities. Instead, opportunities, consumer attitudes, and the existing green practices in pricing and packaging seem to have a stronger influence on green promotion efforts.

The analysis of factors affecting green product design in green marketing reveals several interesting insights. Retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices, opportunities for green marketing practices, and challenges in green marketing show no significant relationship with green product design, as indicated by their respective p-values (0.210, 0.730, and 0.664).

This suggests that even though retailers may be aware of green marketing or perceive opportunities and challenges in this area, these factors do not strongly influence their decisions regarding eco-friendly product design. However, consumer attitudes towards green marketing show a significant positive relationship with green product design (p-value 0.014, coefficient 0.126). This implies that favorable consumer attitudes towards green marketing have a meaningful impact on how retailers design their products. Retailers may respond to consumer preferences by incorporating more sustainable and environmentally friendly elements into their product designs when consumers are more supportive of green initiatives. On the other hand, consumer buying behavior towards green products does not significantly influence green product design (p-value 0.210). Despite consumers' purchasing behaviors, it seems that these patterns do not directly affect how retailers approach green product design. In summary, while consumer attitudes toward green marketing play a crucial role in influencing product design, other factors like awareness, opportunities, and challenges in green marketing, as well as consumer buying behavior, appear to have a limited impact.

The analysis of green disposal practices reveals that most factors examined do not show a significant relationship with how retailers handle the environmentally friendly disposal of products. Specifically, retailers' awareness towards green marketing practices (p-value 0.532), opportunities for green marketing practices (p-value 0.088), consumer buying behavior towards green products (p-value 0.963), consumer attitudes towards green marketing (p-value 0.652), and challenges in green marketing (p-value 0.656) all exhibit non-significant relationships with green disposal practices. This suggests that these factors, despite their relevance to green marketing, do not significantly influence the practices retailers adopt for product disposal. However, there is a notable significant relationship between green marketing practices in respect of green pricing and green disposal practices (p-value < 0.001, coefficient 0.498). This indicates that retailers who implement green pricing strategies are also more likely to engage in green disposal practices. The strong positive relationship suggests that a commitment to sustainable pricing often accompanies a broader strategy that includes responsible disposal practices. Conversely, other aspects of green marketing, such as green packaging and green promotion, do not significantly impact green disposal practices, indicating that these elements may not be as closely aligned with disposal strategies as pricing practices are. Overall, while many elements of green marketing do not directly influence disposal practices, the significant relationship with green pricing highlights the interconnected nature of various green marketing strategies and their collective impact on sustainable practices.

The analysis indicates a significant positive relationship between green product design and green packaging practices (p-value < 0.001, coefficient 0.294). This result suggests that when retailers adopt eco-friendly packaging practices, they are more likely to also implement green product design strategies. The strong positive coefficient implies that an emphasis on sustainable packaging often accompanies a commitment to designing products in an environmentally responsible manner. This relationship underscores the integrated approach that retailers may take towards green marketing, where advancements in one area, such as packaging, positively influence practices in another, like product design. This interconnected approach reflects a broader commitment to sustainability and enhances the overall effectiveness of green marketing strategies.

The analysis of the success of retailers in relation to various green marketing practices shows varying degrees of impact. Green marketing practices in respect of green product design (p-value < 0.001, coefficient 0.220) and green marketing practices in respect of green disposal (p-value < 0.001, coefficient 0.203) exhibit significant positive relationships with retailer success.

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This suggests that retailers who invest in sustainable product design and responsible disposal practices tend to experience greater success, reflecting the positive impact of these green practices on their overall performance and market acceptance. Conversely, green marketing practices in respect of green promotion show a significant negative relationship with retailer success (p-value < 0.001, coefficient -0.297). This indicates that, contrary to expectations, extensive promotion of green practices may not necessarily correlate with retailer success, potentially due to factors such as oversaturation or mismatch between promotional efforts and consumer expectations. Green marketing practices in respect of green pricing (p-value < 0.001, coefficient 0.592) show a significant positive relationship, implying that effective green pricing strategies contribute substantially to retailer success. This is likely because green pricing can enhance perceived value and attract environmentally conscious consumers. Green marketing practices in respect of green packaging (p-value 0.173) does not show a significant relationship, suggesting that while sustainable packaging is important, it may not directly influence retailer success as strongly as other green marketing practices do. In summary, successful retailers are more likely to engage in green product design, effective green pricing, and responsible green disposal, while green promotion does not always translate into success, possibly reflecting a need for alignment between promotional strategies and market needs.

The analysis of consumer satisfaction towards green marketing reveals several insights into the impact of various green marketing practices. Green marketing practices in respect of green product design (p-value 0.995), green promotion (p-value 0.825), green pricing (p-value 0.970), and green disposal (p-value 0.661) show no significant relationship with consumer satisfaction. This indicates that these aspects of green marketing do not directly influence how satisfied consumers feel about green marketing efforts, suggesting that factors beyond these practices may be more critical in shaping consumer satisfaction. However, green marketing practices in respect of green packaging (p-value < 0.001, coefficient 0.287) exhibit a significant positive relationship with consumer satisfaction. This finding implies that consumers respond positively to sustainable packaging, and it plays a crucial role in enhancing their overall satisfaction with green marketing initiatives. This suggests that effective green packaging can improve consumer perceptions and satisfaction. Additionally, challenges in green marketing (p-value < 0.001, coefficient -0.259) show a significant negative relationship with consumer satisfaction. This indicates that difficulties faced by retailers in implementing green marketing practices negatively affect consumer satisfaction, likely because these challenges may lead to inconsistent or less effective green marketing efforts. Success of the retailers (p-value 0.994) does not significantly impact consumer satisfaction, suggesting that the perceived success of retailers does not necessarily translate into greater consumer satisfaction with green marketing. In summary, while green packaging significantly enhances consumer satisfaction, other green marketing practices and the challenges faced in green marketing have less direct influence on consumer satisfaction. This underscores the importance of focusing on effective packaging and addressing marketing challenges to improve consumer perceptions and satisfaction.

Table – 3

Model Fit Summary for opportunities, challenges and motivational factors of green marketing with special reference to Tamilnadu

Indices	Value	Suggested Value
Chi-square value	214.919	
P value	0.006	>0.05 (Hair et al., 1998)
CMIN/DF	1.295	< 5 (Marsh&Hocevar,1985)
GFI	0.946	>0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
AGFI	0.902	>0.90 (Hair et al. 2006)
CFI	0.956	>0.90 (Daire et al., 2008)
RMR	0.088	<0.08 (Hair et al. 2006)
RMSEA	0.031	<0.08 (Hair et al. 2006)

Source: Output generated from Amos 20

The model fit summary for the study on green marketing practices in Tamil Nadu reveals a generally strong fit with the data. Although the chi-square value is 214.919 with a p-value of 0.006, indicating some statistical significance that may suggest a slight misfit, other indices show favorable results. The CMIN/DF ratio is 1.295, well below the recommended maximum of 5, signifying that the model's complexity is appropriately balanced. The Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) stands at 0.946, and the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) is 0.902, both exceeding their respective thresholds of 0.90, which indicates a good fit between the model and the data. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is notably high at 0.956, suggesting that the model is a strong improvement over a null model. The Root Mean Square Residual (RMR) is 0.088, slightly above the ideal threshold of 0.08, and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is excellent at 0.031, well below the recommended maximum of 0.08. These results collectively suggest that while there is a slight indication of model misfit, the overall model demonstrates a very good fit to the data, indicating that it effectively represents the relationships among the variables under study.

1.7. MAIN FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. **Demographic Factors:** The analysis shows that demographic factors such as gender, marital status, occupation, monthly income, and age do not significantly impact consumer buying behavior towards green products. However, educational qualification has a significant positive relationship, indicating that consumers with higher education levels are more likely to purchase green products due to greater environmental awareness. Marketers should therefore focus on educational content and target educated consumers to enhance green product adoption.
2. **Retailer Awareness:** Retailers' awareness of green marketing practices is significantly influenced by the nature of their ownership and consumer buying behavior towards green products. The type of ownership (independent vs. chain) affects retailer awareness, and increased consumer demand for green products drives greater retailer involvement in green marketing. This highlights the importance of consumer behavior in shaping retailer engagement with green marketing.
3. **Consumer Attitudes:** Consumer attitudes towards green marketing are significantly affected by retailers' awareness of green marketing practices. When retailers are more knowledgeable about green marketing, consumer attitudes towards green marketing become more positive. This underscores the impact of retailer education on shaping consumer perceptions of green marketing.

4. **Retailer Opinions on Opportunities and Challenges:** Retailers' opinions on green marketing opportunities are not significantly influenced by factors like sales volume or marketing experience. Similarly, most operational factors do not significantly impact their perception of challenges in green marketing, except for the number of outlets which has a near-significant relationship. However, consumer buying behavior significantly affects the challenges faced in green marketing, suggesting that lower consumer demand leads to greater perceived challenges.
5. **Green Marketing Practices:**
 - **Green Pricing:** Consumer attitudes and buying behavior significantly influence green pricing practices. Positive consumer attitudes and higher engagement in purchasing green products lead to more favorable pricing for green products.
 - **Green Packaging:** Retailers' awareness of green marketing practices and perceived opportunities positively influence green packaging practices. Additionally, consumer buying behavior significantly affects the adoption of green packaging.
 - **Green Promotion:** Opportunities for green marketing and consumer attitudes significantly impact green promotion. However, when consumers are already engaged in purchasing green products, retailers may invest less in promotion. Green pricing and packaging are also strongly associated with green promotion efforts.
 - **Green Product Design:** Favorable consumer attitudes significantly influence green product design. Retailers incorporate more sustainable elements into product designs when consumers show strong support for green initiatives.
6. **Green Disposal:** The analysis reveals that green disposal practices are significantly related to green pricing. Retailers who adopt green pricing strategies are more likely to also engage in responsible disposal practices. Other green marketing aspects do not significantly impact disposal practices.
7. **Retailer Success:** Green marketing practices related to product design, disposal, and pricing positively impact retailer success, while green promotion has a negative relationship with success. This suggests that effective green pricing and sustainable product design contribute to retailer success, whereas extensive green promotion may not always correlate with success.
8. **Consumer Satisfaction:** Green packaging significantly enhances consumer satisfaction, while other green marketing practices do not have a significant direct impact on satisfaction. Additionally, challenges in green marketing negatively affect consumer satisfaction, indicating that overcoming these challenges is crucial for maintaining consumer satisfaction.

These findings collectively highlight the importance of focusing on educational aspects, consumer attitudes, and specific green marketing practices like packaging and pricing to enhance both consumer satisfaction and retailer success in green marketing initiatives.

1.8. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Marketing strategies should target educated consumers, as there is a strong correlation between educational qualifications and green product purchasing behavior. Campaigns should be developed to emphasize the environmental and sustainability benefits of green products, aligning with the interests of this informed demographic.

2. To improve the integration of green marketing practices, it is essential to increase retailer awareness through comprehensive training and resources. This will equip retailers with the knowledge to implement green marketing in their business strategies. Moreover, the awareness programs should be tailored to address the specific needs of different retailer ownership structures, whether independent retailers or chains, to ensure better engagement with green marketing.
3. Marketing strategies should capitalize on favorable consumer attitudes toward green products. By understanding and tapping into these positive attitudes, businesses can craft messages and promotions that resonate with consumer values and preferences. Additionally, engaging consumers who already support green products can further enhance these attitudes and encourage word-of-mouth promotion.
4. Green pricing should be optimized by adjusting strategies based on consumer attitudes and behavior. Offering discounts or promotions on green products can make them more appealing to price-sensitive consumers. Sustainable packaging is also crucial, as it significantly impacts consumer satisfaction. Promotional efforts should focus on highlighting green practices such as eco-friendly packaging and product design, creating a cohesive and compelling green marketing message.
5. Strategies must be developed to overcome barriers faced by retailers, such as market resistance and high costs, to ensure smoother implementation of green marketing practices. Educational campaigns and incentives can be used to increase consumer demand for green products, thereby reducing the perceived challenges of adopting green marketing.
6. A holistic approach to green marketing is essential. By integrating green practices across product design, packaging, pricing, and disposal, businesses can ensure consistency in their green marketing efforts. This approach strengthens the overall effectiveness of green marketing and enhances brand credibility.

1.9 CONCLUSION

The analysis highlights that while many demographic and operational factors do not significantly impact green marketing practices, certain key factors play a crucial role in shaping consumer behavior and retailer success. Educational qualification is a significant predictor of green product purchasing, and retailer awareness of green marketing practices is essential for effective implementation. Consumer attitudes and behavior significantly influence various aspects of green marketing, including pricing, packaging, and promotion. Retailers who effectively integrate green marketing practices into their business strategies, particularly in product design and pricing, are more likely to achieve success. Positive consumer attitudes towards green marketing contribute to reduced challenges and enhanced satisfaction with green products. Conversely, extensive promotion of green practices alone may not always translate into success, indicating the need for alignment between promotional strategies and actual consumer demand. By focusing on educational content, enhancing retailer awareness, and leveraging consumer attitudes, marketers can improve both consumer satisfaction and retailer performance in green marketing. Addressing the challenges in green marketing and adopting an integrated approach to green practices will further strengthen the effectiveness of green marketing initiatives and contribute to greater overall success.

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